

SPEED AND STRENGTH TRAINING OF KURASH WRESTLERS

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Annotation: the article discusses the features of the development of strength and speed-strength qualities of wrestlers. An analysis of scientific and methodological literature shows that good physical training is the basis for improving all aspects of a wrestler's training, and it needs to be given great attention to both beginners and high-class athletes.

Key words: Kurash wrestling, speed-strength qualities, physical qualities, sports, physical exercises.

Introduction. Modern world achievements in sports training of martial artists are so great that without physical training from a young age one cannot count on high results in adulthood as an athlete [1, 2]. Therefore, training young kurash wrestlers is one of the main tasks in preparing a sports reserve and raising the prestige of kurash wrestling in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Issues related to the physical training of young athletes are the most relevant when constructing the educational and training process, and the development of physical qualities of athletes, the process of developing technical skill and the further growth of sports and technical results depend on how rationally they are resolved [3, 4, 5].

The physical qualities of a kurash wrestler, the features of their development in the age aspect are important, since it is the foundation of all sports skills, the formation of basic motor abilities for sports wrestling, that is laid precisely in adolescence [6, 7, 8].

Features of the development of motor abilities are characteristic of each sport and are determined by motivation, goals, history of the development of the sport, and the rules of sports activity. In order to make the right decision aimed at improving motor action, it is necessary to know how a specific sports action is organized and under what conditions. It is necessary to methodically correctly carry out and successfully organize the educational process during sports training, where it is necessary to have knowledge of the patterns of development, formation and targeted improvement of various aspects of the motor function of children and adolescents [9, 10, 11].

Physical fitness is the basis of sports training. It is impossible to achieve high sports results even with good technical and tactical preparedness, if such physical qualities as strength and speed, endurance and flexibility, and agility are not sufficiently developed.

It has been established that high-class wrestlers have well-developed speed, explosive and muscular strength, endurance, agility and flexibility. Therefore, the predominant importance in the development of physical qualities will contribute not only to the possession of high performance, but also to the athlete's achievement of high sports results in wrestling [12, 13, 14, 15].

Kurash wrestling is characterized by a significant amount of load carried out in complex variable situations, which places high demands on the speed of motor reactions and strength, on the wrestler's ability to instantly make optimal decisions and perform effective technical and tactical actions at the highest possible speed [16, 17, 18] .

Therefore, the ever-growing competition in martial arts requires the development of new, more effective means and methods of sports training that would meet the requirements for wrestling. At the same time, the question arises about improving the speed-strength training of young athletes, aimed at achieving high sports results in competitive matches and more successful conduct of both educational and training activities and competitive activities in general.

The practical activity of sports shows that physical exercises are characterized by different directions of influence on the state of the athlete's body. Therefore, the effectiveness of the development of speed and strength qualities is integrally related to the specific gravity of the means and methods used.

The development of speed-strength abilities can be influenced by various exercises of regional and global impact. Although, when it comes to the development of physical qualities specific to any sport, the most appropriate are specially selected exercises that are close in the nature of neuromuscular efforts and structure to motor actions in a particular sport. This provision on the need to select the technology of the training process, based on the motor specificity of a particular sports exercise, was one of the most valuable achievements of sports methodology [2, 10].

When choosing means and technologies for strength training, it is necessary to monitor the basic parameters of movement and the dynamics of muscle tension. A number of authors [12] identify three groups of exercises for developing the explosive strength of a weight wrestler:

- 1) exercises with significant weights (80-90% of the maximum);
- 2) exercises with light weights (80% of the maximum), performed at high speed;
- 3) exercises with competitive weights, performed at maximum speed.

Physical exercise with maximum weight increases absolute strength and promotes the effective development of explosive abilities [4].

Physical exercises with light weight while maintaining a specific movement structure make it possible to improve technical motor actions and their elements at a higher speed than competitive speed, which has a positive effect on the development of explosive abilities [2].

When performing competitive weight training regimens, along with the development of explosive strength, technique is also improved, since in such exercises the external and internal structure of the motor action is preserved.

In combat sports, to develop speed-strength abilities, a number of authors [1, 3, 5, 9] propose the following methods: non-limiting effort, impact, maximum effort, variable, circular and repeated.

The non-limiting effort method is characterized by performing physical exercises not with maximum weight, but with maximum speed. This method solves the problem of developing the so-called “explosive strength”, which is of great importance for achieving success in wrestling, since attacking, counterattacking and defensive actions are performed within the framework of direct athletic combat with the enemy. Criteria for developing explosive strength:

- concentration of muscle efforts and preliminary deformation. Improving the ability to concentrate muscular efforts in conditions of compliance with the specifics of wrestling and, in particular, identity with the nature and mode of operation of muscle groups when performing technical motor actions;
- special exercises. When training a martial artist’s speed-strength abilities and explosive qualities, it is necessary to use physical exercises with various types of weights. However, a requirement common to all weights should be that at each training session the athlete must perform the number of physical exercises in which he is able to repeat the exercises with a given weight without reducing speed.

In this regard, when improving explosive strength and coordination abilities, it is advisable to use alternating weights:

- 1) the weights are initially less, and then more than the competition weight (the weight of the weights is selected as a percentage of the athlete’s maximum result);
- 2) at first there are more weights, and then less than competition;
- 3) the burden is initially less, and then equal to the competitive one;
- 4) the weights are initially greater, and then equal to the competition level.

The impact method of developing the explosive qualities of the muscle groups of the legs consists of significant stimulation as a result of jumping from a certain height, as well as a combination of jumping with a subsequent high or long jump. The level of resistance is determined by your own body weight and the height of the fall.

With the repeated method, it is recommended to use a force of 50-80% force, carried out with maximum speed with a small number of repetitions - this is an explosive force. In the practice of training martial artists, efforts of 20-40% are usually associated with a relatively large number of repetitions and, as a result, develop strength endurance for speed work to a greater extent.

A positive effect in the development of explosive strength can be achieved using the competitive method. The optimal means of influencing specific muscle groups will be the technical motor actions themselves. One of the private methodological techniques in the preparation of highly qualified athletes is a specialized exercise (technical motor action) performed for the result - test throws of a dummy.

During the expression of speed-strength qualities, muscles will usually work in a combination of yielding and overcoming modes. However, there are situations when, with a yielding mode, significant tension will be created in the muscles, which is why, during the overcoming work of such muscles, the magnitude of the expression of force will increase significantly.

To develop and improve speed-strength qualities, some coaches resort to wrestling on the ground, and this allows them to solve several global problems of special speed-strength training. Wrestling in a prone position can be used when working with athletes of any level of preparedness and at various stages of preparation, but techniques on the ground are most often performed in a power mode and only some elements have a speed-strength orientation.

Conclusions. So, to ensure the development of “explosive” force, you can use throwing and pushing various medicine balls, cannonballs, weights and stones from different positions with the greatest acceleration in the final part; activities with an ax and hammers; jerks and pushes of any barbell; as well as overcoming the inertia of your body during strikes, during defense, during transitions from defense to strikes and vice versa. A successful and frequently used exercise for ensuring the development of strength in the extensor muscles of the arms, which bear the main load in striking actions, is considered to be various push-ups while lying down.

No less attention should be paid to strengthening the abdominal muscles. In addition, various exercises on the horizontal bar, parallel bars, gymnastic wall, with shock absorbers and weights, and with partners are also widely used for athletic training. The proposed strength exercises and their complexes should be used at least twice a week. Most often, the tasks of developing various strength skills are solved in the second half (or at the end) of the main part of the lesson. In this case, it is also possible to build a training from several complex “blocks”, in each of which the tasks of reviewing and improving technique, developing strength and flexibility are solved in a consistent manner. If the level of strength development is not high, you can also conduct additional strength training in the athletic training room, on the school sports field, at home, or increase the strength load during morning physical exercises. At the same time, stretching and relaxation of muscles that receive increased force load are considered mandatory.

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